

Modification of Russian made Isotopic Mass-Spectrometer MN 1305 for Organic Research

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The Russian made double-beam mass spectrometer, model MN 1305, was installed in the Chemistry Department of the Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, in February 1967. Originally this instrument was designed for measurement of isotopic ratios of gases, liquids and solids. We now wish to report here the main modifications carried out in order to make it suitable for the use of organic chemists. The modified mass spectrometer has been successfully used by us for the determination of the mass spectra of a large number of organic compounds, mainly natural products. The results thus obtained are being separately published elsewhere.

The characteristics of model MN 1305 mass spectrometer are briefly as follows. It uses the well-known 60° sector type geometry giving direction focussing only. There are three kinds of ion-sources (i) gas, (ii) ribbon and (iii) oven, provided with the machine. The positive ions produced in the ionisation chamber by intercollision between electrons (the ionisation potential range 5 to 90 volts) and sample vapour is drawn out by a constant electric field (accelerated voltage 2KV giving mass number range 1 – 400 ; or 4 KV giving mass number range 1 – 200) and focussed into a narrow beam by a precision ion-optical system. The beam passes through a uniform but continuously varying electromagnetic field, produced by an electromagnet with trapezoidal pole pieces (maximum field strength 7000 oerteds, and electromagnet supply current range 5 to 400 mA). On emerging from the analyser chamber the ion beam strikes the collector plate through a narrow slit in the ion detector generating an electric current which is fed to two d.c. amplifiers with linear response (maximum sensitivity of ion current amplifiers No. 1 : 5×10^{-14} A, and No. 2 : 5×10^{-16} A.).

By continuously varying the magnetic field strength, ions with respective mass/charge ratio are separated and recorded by pen and ink chart recorder. The resolution of the instrument is 350 with the accepted overlap of 5%. In principle by keeping accelerated voltage constant at 1 KV, the upper limit can be raised up to 800 mass number. The mass spectrometer uses two mercury diffusion pumps and there is always present traces of mercury vapour, and consequently a mercury spectrum, which incidentally, helps to calculate mass numbers (besides the usual 18, 28, 32, 44 etc., lines). Sometimes, the doubly charged mercury (Hg^{++}) 102, 101, 100.5, 100, 99.5, 99 lines are also used as reference lines.

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The original inlet system fitted to the machine for the isotopic work proved to be unsuitable for organic research. Hence, we designed a modified inlet system for the introduction of organic solids, liquids, with as short as 'inlet-ionisation-chamber' path as possible. The metal-glass inlet system designed and fabricated in this Laboratory (Fig. 1a) is directly connected to the gas-ion-source.

Clean and dry all glass ampoule (1 b) containing the sample, is prepared in such a way that the tube A-B is separated from the other side at point B by a hair-thin seal. The sample to be analysed is dropped through the opening D till it reaches the area around B and then sealed at point C under vacuum (10^{-2} to 10^{-3} m m.). Two or more such sample tubes are connected to a common glass stem at different heights to form the inlet system I a. This is then screwed on to the specially provided threaded stud on the ion source. At appropriate time the hair thin capillary seal is broken with the help of a magnetic stainless steel ball, raised or lowered by a pair of powerful magnets. The stainless steel ball is then returned to a pocket until further necessary. The entire system is kept hot or cold by suitable means till the spectra are recorded (at least two times) which usually takes about $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The instrument is of double beam type, but since single beam is sufficient for organic research, we have been operating only the most sensitive ion-current amplifier provided on the machine.

The oven in the oven ion-source is situated very close to the ionisation chamber (about 3 to 4 mm. away) and as a result it gives us an opportunity to use it as 'Direct inlet' system. The disadvantage in the process is that it necessitates replacing

the normally used gas ion-source by oven ion-source. Even if two successive samples are to be taken by direct inlet method, one has to take out the ion-source, place fresh sample in the oven, connect it again, wait for the operating vacuum to reach etc. The built-in electrical circuit which heats the oven in the oven ion-source, has been used to heat the vapour leading-tube inside the normally used gas ion-source in conjunction with glass-metal inlet system Ia. A little modification in the electrical layout permitted us to supply high voltage only to the oven-heater while using oven ion-source and disconnect it automatically while using gas-ion source and inlet system Ia. The amount of vapour of the samples admitted into the ion-source of the mass-spectrometer is controlled by heating or cooling the ampoule by suitable means as required by circumstances.

The mass spectra of camphor ($C_{10}H_{16}O$, M. wt. 152) and cholesterol ($C_{27}H_{46}O$, M. wt. 386) recorded on this machine using inlet system a are given below. They compare very well with the spectra available in the literature^{1,2}.

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